

USAGE OF MULTIMEDIA IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract: *Teaching process is difficult and delicate process while teachers are teaching foreign languages. Because for choosing methods or pedagogical techniques teacher should have pedagogical competencies. That's why, this article describes the usage of multimedia in English teaching process to teach FLT effectively.*

Key words: *communication, visual, technology, audio, motivation, animation*

Nowadays, the stereotyped traditional teaching methods and environment are unpopular while multimedia technology featuring audio, visual animation effects naturally and humanely makes us more access to information besides, with such characteristics as abundant-information and crossing time and space, multimedia technology offers a sense of reality and functions very well, which greatly cultivates students' interest and motivation in study and their involvement in class activities. To Promote Students' Communication Capacity: Traditional teaching has hampered students' capacity to comprehend certain language and also understanding to structure, meaning and function of the language, and makes the students passive recipients of knowledge, So, it is hard to achieve the target of communication. With teachers' instructions leading students' thought patterns and motivating students' emotions, the multimedia technology seeks integration of teaching and learning and provides the students greater incentives, The PPT courseware activate students' thinking; the visual and vivid courseware can help them to transform English learning into capacity cultivation. And such in-class activities as group discussion, subject discussion, and debates can also offer more opportunities for communication

among students and between teachers and students. So multimedia technology teaching has uniquely inspired students' positive thinking and communication skills in social practice [4, 286p.].

To Widen Students' Knowledge to Gain an Insightful Understanding to Western Culture: The multimedia courseware can offer the students abundant information; more plentiful than textbooks, and help them to get of displays vivid cultural background, rich content and true-to-life language materials, which are much natural and closer to life. Not only could learners improve their listening ability, but also learn the western culture. Grasping information through various channels can equip; the students with knowledge and bring about information-sharing among students and make them actively participate in class discussion and communication. To Improve Teaching Effect: Multimedia teachings enrich teaching content and make the best of class time and break the "teacher centered" teaching pattern and fundamentally improve class efficiency. Due to large classes it is difficult for the students to have speaking communication. The utilization of multimedia sound lab materializes the individualized and co-operative teaching. The traditional teaching model mainly emphasized on teachers' instruction, and the information provided is limited due to traditional classes. On the contrary, multimedia technology goes beyond time and space, creates more vivid, visual, authentic environment for English learning, stimulates students' initiatives and economizes class time meanwhile increases class information. To Improve Interaction Between Teacher and Student: Multimedia teaching stresses the role of students, and enhances the importance of "interaction" between teachers and students. A major feature of multimedia teaching is to train and improve students' ability to listen and speak, and to develop their communicative competence, during this process, the teacher's role as a facilitator is particularly prominent. Using multimedia in context creation creates a good platform for the exchange between teachers and students, while at the same time providing a language environment that

improves on the traditional classroom teaching model. In this way, teachers in the classroom no longer blindly input information and force students to receive it in a passive way.

Creates a Context for Language teaching: Multimedia teaching creates a context for language teaching. This method makes the class lively and interesting, as well as optimizing the organization of the class. Multimedia has its own features such as visibility and liveliness. During the process of multimedia English teaching, sounds and pictures can be set together, which enhances the initiative of both teachers and students, when using multimedia software, teachers can use pictures and images to enrich the content of classes, and also imagine different contexts in the process of producing teaching courseware, Students in the class can use multimedia to understand the class in a clear way. Through the whole interactive process, it is apparent that using multimedia in ELT is effective in nurturing students' interest in learning English, as well as enhancing teachers' interest in English teaching. As through Multimedia and network technology we can offer students not only rich, sources of authentic learning materials, but also an attractive and a friendly interface, vivid pictures and pleasant sounds, which to a large extent overcomes the lack of authentic language environment and arouses students' interest in learning English. **To Provide Flexibility to Course Content:** In addition, multimedia teaching is also flexible. It is obvious that the context can be created not only in the classroom, but also after class. Multimedia language teaching can also create a multimedia language environment for the purpose of conducting language teaching. English teaching itself must focus on the guidance of teachers and be student-centered, which we believe is one of the principles for language teaching. Students are bound to have some problems in classroom teaching, which can be addressed under the guidance of teachers. In such circumstances, students can use the new technology to their advantage, such as manipulating the network to contact teachers, and receiving answers by email.

The list of literature

1. Gay S.M. Teaching with technology: A case study of teachers' perceptions of implementing computers into the classroom. ETD Collection for University of Nebraska. 2005. 395P.
2. Goodwin K. Use of tablet technology in the classroom. South Wales, Sydney: NSWCurriculum and Learning Innovation Centre. 2007. 426P.
3. Karimova Umida. (2022). The Role of Teaching Compounds According to Types of Speech in Constructivism. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 8, 4–9. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/1325>
4. KarimovaUmida. (2022). THE WAYS OF USING CONSTRUCTIVISM TO TEACHING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND VOCABULARY FOR EFL. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 449–454. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SCXJ2>
5. Ismailov A. R. CONSCIOUS REGULATION OF EMOTIONS AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF EFFECTIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS //ХАБАРИШЫСЫ. – 2021. – Т. 1. – С. 302.
6. Ismailov A. R. THE PROBLEM OF THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN MODERN METHODICS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2021. – №. 4-8. – С. 46-49.
7. Ismailov A. R. STYLISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECT IN DISCOURSE ANALYSIS //Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe. – 2018. – №. 4-4. – С. 62-65.
8. Ismailov A. R., Nasrullaev J. R. PRINCIPLES OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR ORAL SPEECH //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 60.

9. JAHONOVNA S. S., FURQATOVNA S. Y., QIZI X. Z. X. Make Use of Interactive Forms and Methods in Teaching a Foreign Language //JournalNX. – Т. 6. – №. 11. – С. 260-263.
10. Obidjonovna M. F. SOME TEACHING PRINCIPLES OF READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 23. – №. 1. – С. 18-20.
11. Boltakulova G. TEMPORALITY AND ITS PECULIARITIES IN THE STRUCTURE OF ENGLISH SENTENCES //Scientific enquiry in the contemporary world: theoretical basics and innovative approach. – 2016. – С. 71.
12. Boltakulova G. F. MEANS OF EXPRESSING AND ANALYZING ADVERBIAL MODIFIER OF TIME IN THE SENTENCE STRUCTURE IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN //DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPOKEN AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE AT THE CURRENT STAGE OF THE INTENSIVE INFORMATION TURNOVER. – 2015. – С. 11-12.
13. Амриддинова Н. Ш. PECULIARITIES OF SUPPLY AND DIFFICULTIES IN THE RESEARCH OF VARIATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL MEANING IN VOCABULARY ARTICLES //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 6.
14. Шомуродова Ш. Ж. КОНТЕКСТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКОГО ЗНАЧЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ //Научные школы. Молодежь в науке и культуре XXI в. – 2017. – С. 240-241.
15. Шомуродова Ш. Ж. Теоретические предпосылки фразеологической деривации //Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2010. – №. 22. – С. 148-150.
16. Шомуродова Ш. Ж., Назарова Н. Б., Акрамова К. BARRIERS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN JUNIOR CLASSES //ЕВРАЗИЙСКИЙ НАУЧНЫЙ. – 2020. – С. 63.

